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BUYING PATTERN OF CONSUMER IN ONLINE STORE: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY

Roopesh Rao

Assistant Professor,
Datta Meghe Institute Of Management Studies,
Atrey Layout, Nagpur-440022, India

Sachin Gurve

Manager –Training,
Pearson Education Services, Bangalore India

Pranali Ghugre

Student, Datta Meghe Institute Of Management Studies,
Atrey Layout, Nagpur-440022, India

Abstract

Today Internet is not only a networking media, but also as a means of transaction for consumers at global market. Internet usage has grown rapidly over the past years and it has become common means for delivering and trading information, services and goods.

Indian consumers as a whole spend about 55% of the total consumption expenditure on food items. According to a survey conducted by ORG, the expenditure on non-food items has recorded large growth that the expenditure on food items. Consumers decide whether, what, when, from whom, where and how much to buy. They can avail various mediums to buy the products. But currently we are living in the age of internet. This study bring about the details about the buying pattern of consumer in online store”

Key words: *Networking Media, Global Market, Internet, Online Store*

Introduction

According to a study, “About 44 percent students use Internet in India and overall 72% of young people access Internet on regular basis. Due to the vast usage of Internet, the buying patterns have been changed. It has changed the way goods are purchased and sold, resulting to the exponential growth in the number of online shoppers. However, a lot of differences concerning online buying have been discovered due to the various consumers’ characteristics and the types of provided products and services. Buying behaviour toward online shopping and goal to shop online are not only affected by ease of use, usefulness, and enjoyment, but also by other factors like consumer individuality, situational factors, product distinctiveness, previous online shopping understanding and faith in online shopping. Therefore, understanding who are the ones consuming and why they choose to use or keep away from the Internet as a distribution channel, is a critical matter for both marketing managers and consumer thinkers.

There are lots of companies which are providing the platform to consumers to buy the products through online. Online consumers tend to be better educated. Higher computer literacy makes internet shopping smarter. Their awareness about the internet also makes them better positioned to identify and take decision for products and services. By the internet, consumers find that they no longer have to accept fixed prices for the products and services and through the click of a few buttons the lowest priced, highest quality product can be found. The concept of online shopping developed gradually, after the launch of the World Wide Web. Charles Stack was the first person to create an online book store in 1992. Even Pizza Hut opened an online pizza shop, whereas eBay and Amazon took the concept of online shopping to an entirely new level. Online shopping began in full swing since the year 1996. Overall, 71 million users accessed Internet in year 2009, with 52 Million “active” users who accessed it at least once in a month.

Internet has made a significant contribution to our lifestyles on account of its abundance and diversity of information. Its penetration is rising markedly in India which has fuelled the growth of e-commerce in the economy. The term e-commerce or electronic commerce refers to shopping on the web. It incorporates a lot of other activities such as B2B transactions and various internal processes that companies use to support their buying, selling, hiring and planning. In terms of magnitude, e-commerce market has grown from 8147 crores in 2007 to 31598 crores by the end of year 2010 (IAMAI, 2011). Broadband connectivity and increased usage of credit cards have provided a favourable infrastructure for the growth of online shopping in India. Continued liberalization in the telecom sector has shown positive effects in the past few years. The Indian Telecom policy recognized the convergence of different media and permitted direct inter-connectivity amongst various service providers. This has paved the way to internet retailing which has become one of the most innovative and challenging contributions to the retail industry. It offers consumers an additional channel for information, service and purchasing along with additional benefits of choice, convenience and cost savings. Global online retailing has gained a significant share in overall retail sales over the past two decades.

Customers rely on purchasing familiar brands in order to reduce the risks associated with their purchase. Privacy concerns have dampened the online consumer enthusiasm in India. There are a number of issues related to security and transaction frauds. High occurrences of failed payments deter the customer to revisit portals for shopping. With regard to the future of retailing in India, the views are divergent. Many experts believe that the future of internet business is very promising and expect its exponential growth in the coming times. Overall, Indian retail business is a rich business waiting to be exploited! It has become imperative for online retailers to understand the buying behaviours and preferences of the internet consumers and devise appropriate business strategies to gain competitive advantage. This study aims at improving the understanding of online consumer behaviour by investigating various factors affecting intention to purchase online.

Online buying behaviour increase value of proposition revolves around giving consumers the power and ease of purchasing fashion and lifestyle products online. Offerings such as the largest in-season product

catalogue, 100% authentic products, cash on delivery; EMI facility and 30 day return policy make Myntra.com, the preferred shopping destination in the country. To make online shopping easier for you, a dedicated customer connect team is on standby to answer your queries 24x7. Online shopping understands its shoppers' needs and caters to them with choice of apparel, accessories, cosmetics and footwear from over 500 leading Indian and international brands.

Consumer behaviour is affected by four categories of factors: cultural factors, social factors, personal factors and psychological factors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The first category of cultural factors, includes terms such as culture, subculture and social class (Armstrong and Kotler, 2003; Peter and Donnelly, 2001, Wu, 2003). The term culture is complex and involves the knowledge, beliefs, arts, laws, ethics, customs and many other abilities and habits that are obtained by an individual just by being part of the society (Hawkins, Best and Coney, 1995). Every culture consists of smaller sub-cultures which contain a more specific identity to their members. There are four categories of sub-cultures: nationalities, religion groups, tribes and geographical locations (Kotler, 1991; Armstrong and Kotler, 2003). Social classes are relatively homogenous and continuous subdivisions of a society, which are arranged hierarchically and whose members have common values, interests and behaviour (Kotler, 1991).

The second category refers to social factors and includes reference groups, family, social roles and social status (Armstrong and Kotler, 2003; Wu, 2003). Reference groups involve all those groups that have a direct (personal) or indirect influence on the buying behaviour or behaviour of an individual (Kotler, 1991; Armstrong and Kotler, 2003). Family is considered the most significant social factor and has been widely examined (Armstrong and Kotler, 2003). There are two types of families the orientation family which consists of the parents and the family that someone creates for oneself (Kotler, 1991). The position of an individual in a group can be defined in terms of social role and social status (Armstrong and Kotler, 2003). The term role contains the actions that a person has to take in relation to the people that surround him / her. Every role is connected to a status which shows the corresponding respect of the society (Kotler, 1991).

The third category, the personal factors, include: age and life circle stage, occupation, economic situation, lifestyle, personality and self-concept (Armstrong and Kotler, 2003; Wu, 2003). People change their preferences in products or services according to their age. Moreover, their purchases are formed throughout their life circle stages which are the phases the families go through while they develop and mature over time (Kotler and Armstrong, 1996). A person's occupation is another factor that influences one's buying behaviour. People of different occupations have different needs and thus purchase different products and services (Kotler, 1991; Kotler and Armstrong, 1996; Armstrong and Kotler, 2003). Many purchasing habits depend on the economic situation of an individual (Adcock *et al*, 1995). The economic data of an individual involve one's income, savings, and disposable capital, borrowing capability and buying behaviour towards consumption regarding savings (Kotler, 1991; Armstrong and Kotler, 2003). Lifestyle is considered to be all the habits one has which are expressed through one's actions, interests, beliefs and small luxuries one indulges oneself with (Adcock *et al*, 1995). Personality regards the psychological characteristics of a person that drive him to reasonable and stable reactions towards one's environment. Last, the presumed image a person has of oneself is complex. It consists of the way a person perceives oneself, the way one wants to be and the way others consider him / her. According to the overall image someone has of oneself, he / she form his / her behaviour (Kotler, 1991; Kotler and Armstrong, 1996; Armstrong and Kotler, 2003).

The fourth category consists of psychological factors like motivation, perception, learning, beliefs and buying behaviours (Armstrong and Kotler, 2003; Wu, 2003; Saprikis, Chouliara and Vlachopoulou, 2010). Motivation is an internal and complex process which influences people's behaviour and is caused by

particular motives such as hunger, thirst, recognition and devotion. Consumers act and react based on their perceptions. The way a motivated person acts is influenced by his / her perception of the given situation. The largest part of human behaviour is learnt. It is said that a person's learning is produced through the interaction of motives, stimuli and reactions (Kotler, 1991; Kotler and Armstrong, 1996; Armstrong and Kotler, 2003). Through acting and learning people form beliefs and buying behaviours that affect their purchasing behaviour. Beliefs are the descriptive way a person thinks of something and are based on knowledge, opinion or faith and may involve sentimental charges, while buying behaviour regards the continuous evaluation, the emotions and the tendencies of a person towards an object or idea (Kotler, 1991; Kotler and Armstrong, 1996; Armstrong and Kotler, 2003).

Companies also use the internet to convey communication and disseminate information, to sell the product, to take feedback and also to conduct satisfaction surveys with customers. Consumers use the internet not only to buy the product online, but also to compare prices, product features and after sale service facilities they will receive if they purchase the product from a particular store. Many experts are optimistic about the prospect of online business.

In addition to the tremendous potential of the E-commerce market, the internet provides a unique opportunity for companies to more efficiently reach existing and potential customers. Although most of the revenue of online transactions comes from business-to-business commerce, the practitioners of business-to-consumer commerce should not lose confidence. It has been more than a decade since business-to-consumer. E-commerce first involved, scholars and practitioners of electronic commerce constantly strive to gain an improved insight into consumer behaviour in cyberspace. Along with the development of E-retailing, researchers continue to explain E-consumers behaviour from different perspectives. Many of their studies have posited new emergent factors or assumptions which are based on the traditional models of consumer behaviour, and then examine their validity in the internet context.

Online shopping basically provides the way consumers go shopping and purchase services and goods with reasonable price on the Internet. For some consumers, shopping and purchasing online have become part of their daily lives, while others may not even care about it. At this point, I wonder what factors influence online purchasing behaviour and explain the difference in online buying behaviour among Internet users.

Having access to online shopping has truly revolutionized and influenced our society as a whole. This use of technology has opened new doors and opportunities that enable for a more convenient lifestyle today. Electronic goods and Airline or Railway ticket reservation tend to be the most sought after products bought online. Online shopping is a different experience and one can make the shopping creative over the internet as one gets used to it. However, we can say that most of the respondents are aware about internet shopping but not shopping online. It is also important for all of us to understand how to shop online safely and wisely. This research study has helped in understanding how many people are buying products and services through online shopping and what is their buying behaviour. (Rajesh Faldu July 2013)

This study attempts to analyze the features related to the buying behaviour of online shoppers. Consumer buying behaviour in respect of online shopping was studied using different socio-economic variables. It also provides a support that helps researchers understand the drivers of consumers' buying behaviour and goal to shop on the Internet, and consumers' perceptions regarding ease of use and usefulness. Conclusions derived from the analysis can be used as useful guide for market orientation. The outcomes of the study suggest that assessment of consumer buying behaviour can contribute to a better understanding of consumer buying behaviour in respect of online shopping. (Ankur Kumar Rastogi July 2010)

In his study on analysis of consumer behaviour online explained that the most relevant behavioural characteristics of online consumers and examine the ways they find, compare and evaluate product information. Comparison of the newly collected survey data with the existing consumer behaviour theory resulted in detection of a number of issues related to a specific consumer group. The purpose of this

report is to translate these findings into a set of implementation activities on strategic and technological level. Execution of these recommendations will result in better conversion of visitors into customers and encourage customer loyalty and referrals. The focus group of this study will be young adults aged between eighteen and thirty-four interested in buying a mobile phone or a related product. (PetrovicDejan 2006)

This report will outline the most relevant behavioural characteristics of online consumers and examine the ways they find, compare and evaluate product information. Comparison of the newly collected survey data with the existing consumer behaviour theory resulted in detection of a number of issues related to a specific consumer group. The purpose of this report is to translate these findings into a set of implementation activities on strategic and technological level. Execution of these recommendations will result in better conversion of visitors into customers and encourage customer loyalty and referrals.

The focus group of this study will be young adults aged between eighteen and thirty-four interested in buying a mobile phone or a related product. (Shun &Yunjie2006)

in their showed that there are product types, which are more likely to be sold online such as software, books, electronics and music. Reason for this is that when purchasing these types of products, one does not require personal inspection and most, if not all features, can be outlined in the product description and images. Most products in the mobile phone family belong to this category. According to the recent research on consumer behaviour on the Internet users (Cotte, Chowdhury, Ratenshwar& Ricci, 2006), there are four distinct consumer groups with different intentions and motivations:

1. Exploration
2. Entertainment
3. Shopping
4. Information.

Majority of young adults interviewed for purpose of this research tend to be active information seekers. A high level of technological confidence within this group tends to be an encouraging factor when it comes to product information research online. The following analysis presents both, focus group results and behavioural theory in a parallel fashion divided into two main research topics:

- Information Retrieval and Search Patterns
- Perception of Product Information Online

These two areas are mutually dependent and particularly important in a market where consumers have the power to choose the right product from a number of competing suppliers.

It is innovative and creative because marketers can experiment with it in form, content, visibility and availability. In Indian online shopping is considered as a relevant alternative channel for retailing and it is now an important part of the retail experience. This research study is an empirical study to find out the motivators and decisional influencers of online shopping. The sample has been selected form the youth population as this group of people actually use major motivator factors which motivate the Indian consumer to buy online. Similarly, reluctance and preference are the two decisional factors which influence the decision. (Bikramjit rishi 2010)

A. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To analyze various factors responsible for purchase pattern of consumer.
- 2) To investigate the impact of emotional state on the consumer of online customer.
- 3) To analyze the how to influence of perceived risk on online purchases and satisfaction.
- 4) To determine the relation between customer loyalty in the case of online consumer.

B. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

At any given time are millions of people online and each of them is a potential customer for a company providing online sales.

Due to the rapid development of the technologies surrounding the internet, a company that is interested in selling products from its web site will constantly has to search for an edge in the tierce competition.

Since there are so many potential consumers, it is of the out most importance to be able to understand what the consumer wants and needs. The importance of analyzing and identifying factors that influence the consumer when he or she decides to purchase on the internet is vital. Since the internet is new medium for there have been new demands set by the consumer. Why it is crucial for the online retailers to know what influences the online consumer.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Source of data:-

a. Primary data:

It is the information collected directly without any reference. In the study it was mainly interviews with concerned customers. Some of the information had verified or supplemented with personal observation, the data collected through conducting the personal interview with the customers. This is through a well designed questionnaire.

b. Secondary data:

The secondary data was collected from already published sources such as pamphlets, annual reports, reports and internal records. The data includes reference from text books and relating to articles published in business details like economic times, business time etc.

2. Research Methodology

Data for this study was collected by means of survey conducted in Nagpur city. The sample size was 100. The Questionnaire (shown in Annexure) was used mainly to test the model proposed for buying behaviour towards online shopping. The type of research was both exploratory as well as descriptive. Likert five point scales ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree was used as a basis of questions. We took around eleven different factors by studying the existing models of consumer buying behaviours that play an important role in online purchase, and then proposed a model leading to online shopping. This model was then tested in our research by the mode of factors analysis in SPSS.

a. Sample Design:

The factors that I intended to examine can be applied to and investigated at any population that uses the internet and buys products online I decided that the sample size should contain over 100 respondents and I collected answers from 100 respondents. The population for this research was people from Nagpur only. Convenience sampling involves using samples that are the easiest to obtain and is continued until the sampling size that is needed is reached. Sample selection is of random type.

b. Sample size:

Sample size is 100 customers.

Hypothesis

1. H0-Awareness of online retail store has signification impact on online shopping.
H1-Awareness of online retail store does not have signification impact on online shopping.

2. H0- Trust on the brand has signification impact on online consumer buying behaviour.
H1- Trust on the brand has no signification impact on online consumer buying behaviour.

3. H0 - Consumers are attracted by cash on delivery services.

H1 - Consumers are not attracted by cash on delivery services.

RESULT & ANALYSIS

1. AGE

- The sample size is 100
- Age of the online buying customer.

Age	No of Respondent
15-20	16
21-25	54
26-30	24
above 30	6
Total	100

DATA INTERPRETATION:

The above diagram shows the percentage with respect to the age of respondent as it shows that from age 15-20 the no of respondent 16% and from the age of 21-25 it is 54% and from 26-30 it is 24% and 30-to above it is 6% this is the above data which is shown by the this pie chart.

2. GENDER:-

Gender	No of Respondent
Male	32
Female	68
Total	100

DATA INTERPRETATION:

In this graph showing more percentage of females rather than male the percentage of female respondent is 68% and percentage of male respondents is only 32%.

3. Qualification:-

Qualification	No of Respondent
HSC	44
Graduation	38
Post Graduation	12
Other	6
Total	100

DATA INTERPRETATION:-

The above diagram shows us the percentage with to the qualification of respondents and its shows the post graduate respondents are more rather than percentage of graduate and others.

4. OCCUPATION

Occupation	No of Respondent
Student	54
Business	14
Service	16
Housewife	16
Total	100

DATA INTERPRETATION:-

This graph help us to know the occupation of the respondents this is to know that which segment of people are buying more product on the internet whether they are the segment of student,service,business or housewife, the above graph shows that the student i.e. 54% of the student are using internet to buy online products.

5. DO YOU SHOP ONLINE?

Do you shop online?	No of Respondent
Yes	82
No	18
Total	100

DATA INTERPRETATION:-

As per the data collection and analysis, it is interpreted that 82% of people use online shopping and 18% of people not use online shopping.

One-Sample Statistics

		Statistic	Bootstrap ^a			
			Bias	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
previous experience helps	N	100				
	Mean	3.44	.01	.12	3.21	3.68
	Std. Deviation	1.225	-.013	.081	1.039	1.358
	Std. Error Mean	.123				
feedback help	N	100				
	Mean	3.36	.01	.12	3.13	3.61
	Std. Deviation	1.251	-.014	.078	1.070	1.377
	Std. Error Mean	.125				
information helps	N	100				
	Mean	3.54	.00	.12	3.31	3.76
	Std. Deviation	1.176	-.010	.087	.980	1.327
	Std. Error Mean	.118				
Advertising	N	100				
	Mean	3.44	.00	.12	3.21	3.67
	Std. Deviation	1.200	-.008	.083	1.029	1.345
	Std. Error Mean	.120				
what do you shop	N	100				
	Mean	2.82	.00	.15	2.53	3.10
	Std. Deviation	1.513	-.008	.054	1.390	1.608
	Std. Error Mean	.151				
cash on delivery	N	100				
	Mean	3.60	.01	.12	3.36	3.83
	Std. Deviation	1.255	-.014	.088	1.055	1.403
	Std. Error Mean	.126				
parent brand	N	100				
	Mean	3.46	.01	.11	3.24	3.68
	Std. Deviation	1.176	-.012	.085	.976	1.314
	Std. Error Mean	.118				

From the above table we can find out the following:

1. We can see that the mean 3.44 which is following between lower tail (3.21) and upper tail (3.68), hence we don't have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.
2. We can see that the mean 3.36 which is following between lower tail (3.13) to upper tail (3.76); hence we don't have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.
3. We can see that the mean 3.54 which is following between lower tail (3.31) to upper tail (3.76), hence we don't have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.
4. We can see that the mean 3.44 which is following between lower tail (3.21) to upper tail (3.67), hence we don't have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.
5. We can see that the mean 2.82 which is following between lower tail (2.53) to upper tail (3.10), hence we don't have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.
6. We can see that the mean 3.60 which is following between lower tail (3.36) to upper tail (3.83), hence we don't have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.
7. We can see that the mean 3.46 which is following between lower tail (3.24) to upper tail (3.68), hence we don't have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Hence from the above results we can conclude that the awareness of online retail store influences online shopping, trust on the brand influence online shopping & consumer attracted by value added services like cash on delivery. The three segments that were found show a significant difference in the primary factor of concern. The general distribution showed that the factor price was the primary factor for the entire population sample, and that second factor was trust was closely followed by convenience. When we segmenting the respondents through the different variables we found that segment one were mainly trust oriented and the respondents had a high positive buying behaviour towards purchasing book online. Other segment was mainly price and convenience oriented therefore took the most consideration to the opinions and experiences of the reference groups. As they low disposable income and were somewhat convenience oriented when acquiring information about low price, we chose to label them price easers. We found that most of the time youngster who are from the age of 20-25 shop a lot on the net rather than other age limits. People used to do online shopping because of its convenience rather than its pricing, but the main thing which is very common in most of the people about online shopping is its risk of privacy i.e. hacking of account number getting passwords and all.

CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a framework for enhancing our understanding of consumers' buying behaviour toward online shopping. The findings suggest that utilitarian orientations, convenience, price and wider selection are an important determinant of consumer's buying behaviour toward online shopping. Moreover they have a significant positive impact on consumers' buying behaviour toward online shopping. Consumers' personality tendency was shown to affect their buying behaviour toward online shopping. Findings was showed utilitarian consumers had higher affect on buying behaviour while hedonic consumers had no significant effect with buying behaviour toward online shopping. Therefore, finding from this study confirmed that shoppers are goal-orientation and have previously been planning their most recent online purchase. Utilitarian shoppers may be inclined to shop through internet in order to increase shopping productivity. On the other hand, consumers' tendency when doing online shopping would be more likely to be utilitarian than hedonic. Therefore e-retailers, which focus on utilitarian customers, should emphasize more user friendly function in order to provide utilitarian customers a way to find what they need efficiently. Moreover, the next aspect of the study is online shopping perceived benefits. The findings of the study also implies that consumers are looking for more convenience(time and

money saving), cheaper prices and wider selection when they shop online, making them as the dominant factors that motivates online consumers in Malaysia to shop online. Consumers who value the convenience, prices and wider selection of Internet shopping tend to purchase more online and more often.

A practical assessment of these dimensions revealed. That individuals who purchase online, perceived significantly greater benefit in terms of convenience and price. Clearly, shopping motivations explain consumer's adoption of the internet as a shopping medium and consequently contribute to innovation adoption research. Therefore, online retailers need to ensure that the online shopping process through their websites and made as easy, simple and convenient for consumers to shop online. Moreover, online retailers need to provide competitive price for products in order to attract online shoppers to their websites and encourage them to make a purchase decision. However, this will lead to intense price competition which is expected to increase even further with the availability of intelligent search engines and comparing shopping agents that enable online consumers to easily compare product offerings from various online retailers. Thus, in order to avoid intense price competition, online retailers need to find other ways to differentiate themselves from their competitors. Therefore, the finding suggests that online retailers need to provide more convenience and competitive price and more variety products in order to attract online shoppers to their websites and encourage them to make purchase decision. However, this will lead to competition among retailers and the level of competition is expected to increase even further with the availability of intelligent search engines and comparing shopping agents that enable consumer to easily obtain product information and compare product offerings from various online retailers.

FUTURE RESEARCH

Future research needs to focus on a larger cross section of Internet users and more diversified random samples to verify the findings of the current study. Moreover, to further studies clarity of the factors influence on attitude toward online shopping, other behavioural model could be used. Future investigation could also examine the causal relationships between factors and how consumers' attitude overall online shopping by employing a structural equation modelling technique.

Certainly, there are other factors that influenced attitude toward online shopping, which have not been included in this study. Enhancement of the model by addition of other relevant variables could produce a model that has more clarifying power. Therefore, future research needs to select the other variables by means of other essential elements such as system, product/service and vendor-related factors that influence consumers' e-shopping behaviour.

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